

Nickel and nitrogen doped bifunctional ORR and HER electrocatalysts derived from CO₂

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Abstract

While non-precious metal catalysts (NPMCs) have been shown to be viable alternatives for Pt-based catalyst materials in both proton exchange membrane fuel cells (PEMFCs) and electrolyzers, all of the synthesis methods of these materials still have a positive carbon footprint. This means that while production of CO₂ is avoided by converting to a hydrogen economy, a large amount of CO₂ must be produced to drive this transition (as much as 600 kg of CO₂ per kilogram of catalyst for CVD-based materials). Here, we demonstrate for the first time a sustainable method for synthesizing a bifunctional ORR and HER catalyst directly from CO₂ in a process that captures carbon dioxide from the atmosphere or flue gases instead of producing it as all previous methods for creating ORR/HER catalysts. The electrocatalytic activity of the material is correlated to its structure and synthesis conditions by a thorough physico-chemical analysis including rotating disk electrode (RDE) measurements, porosity analysis with N₂ physisorption, scanning and transition electron microscopy imaging (SEM,

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TEM) and X-ray analysis of the materials' crystal structure and elemental composition. The material shows promising activity and paves way for a dual approach on reducing the CO₂ footprint of the energy economy.

Keywords: Oxygen reduction, Hydrogen evolution, Non-precious metal catalysts, Molten salt, Carbon capture, CO₂ reduction

Introduction

As the economy of the world continues to develop, energy consumption grows across all sectors of the economy. The transportation sector makes up 21% of the global energy consumption and nearly all of the energy used for that is still based on burning fossil fuels.¹ Due to that it's in utmost importance to find alternatives that leave a smaller carbon footprint on the environment. A potential future power source that has attracted a lot of attention is the PEMFC. Such a device can generate electricity efficiently from clean and renewable fuels (H₂). Hydrogen in the form of compressed hydrogen or hydrides, for example and oxygen from the air are transformed into electricity, water and heat electrochemically. Hydrogen is oxidized on the anode, while the cathode reaction is always the electrochemical reduction of oxygen (ORR). Due to ORR's sluggish kinetics the overpotential of ORR it contributes the most to the efficiency losses in a fuel cell. To overcome this, an effective electrocatalyst is needed. At the current technical stage, the most practical catalysts used in PEMFCs are platinum (Pt) or alloy-based materials, but the limited reserves, high cost and instability over long-term operations hinder its large-scale application. Therefore great attention is devoted to creating non-precious metal or metal free catalysts, to make fuel cells actually sustainable.^{2,3} The reverse device for the PEMFC, the PEM electrolyzer, works by splitting water into hydrogen and oxygen using the same basic principle as the PEM fuel cell. PEM electrolyzers face the same problem as PEMFCs, as catalysts are also needed to drive the oxygen evolution

reaction (OER, cathode reaction) and the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER, anode reaction).⁴ A variety of advanced materials, such as metallenes, 2D nanomaterials, transition metal nitrides and chalcogenides, N-doped carbon-cobalt borides, metal-organic frameworks (MOFs), nickel indium spinels and doped aerogels have been developed to replace platinum on both the cathode and anode of the PEMFC.^{5,6,15–21,7–14}

NPMCs have shown promising activities at both high and low pH, but lack stability in comparison with Pt/C, especially in harsh fuel cell or electrolyzer conditions. The main reasons for activity loss are demetallation, protonation/anion binding, generation of H₂O₂ and flooding of micropores, which leads to enhanced mass transport losses. One of many researched NPMCs is transition metal-nitrogen-carbon catalyst (M-N-C).^{22,23} M-N-C catalysts are commonly grouped into two: catalysts employing atomically dispersed M-N_x active sites and catalysts based on metal (such as Fe or Ni) or metal oxide nanoparticles encapsulated in nitrogen doped carbon.^{4,24–27} Another potential alternative for Pt/C catalyst that has gained a lot of attention is metal-free carbon nanomaterial. Since pure carbon materials have relatively low electrocatalytic activity, doping them with nitrogen significantly increases their stability and activity for the ORR and HER at both high and low pH values. To develop high-performance catalysts it's important to have high concentration of active sites, hence it is necessary to identify which configuration of nitrogen (pyridinic, graphitic, pyrrolic) is mainly responsible for the ORR and HER activity.^{28,29,30,31,32–34}

Recently, a new method of synthesizing carbon nanomaterials based on CO₂ electrolysis has emerged, where a carbonate salt mixture is used as electrolyte.^{35–41} In this method, the carbonate salt is split into solid carbon and oxygen gas. The carbonate salt itself is then regenerated from CO₂ which is captured from the surrounding atmosphere or flown through or over the electrolyte.^{35,42} Molten salts have many advantages for CO₂ electrolysis such as a

low cost and toxicity, high ionic conductivity, concentration of carbon, and a wide electrochemical and temperature window.⁴³ The structure and morphology of the resulting carbon product can be controlled by choosing electrolysis conditions (electrodes, applied current and duration).⁴⁴ An addition of Ni⁺ to the electrolyte is known to increase the degree of graphitization of the final carbon product, creating CNTs in pure lithium carbonate and other graphitized structures in melts containing secondary alkali cations such as K⁺ or Na⁺.^{45–}
⁴⁷ An increase in the degree of graphitization of the carbon material significantly increases the overall stability, conductivity and catalytic activity of the material towards both the HER and ORR and its stability during operation, both of which can be close to a Pt/C catalyst in alkaline solutions. Thanks to the low cost, sustainable and abundant source material and environmental friendliness of the process itself it's a promising way towards the rational design of new and highly active ORR and HER electrocatalysts.^{48,49}

The purpose of this research is to demonstrate highly active Ni and N co-doped bifunctional ORR and HER catalysts synthesized directly from CO₂. The physical properties and electrocatalytic activity of carbon materials synthesized from CO₂ were compared to create synthesis-structure-activity correlations and to note the modifications in the materials during nitrogen doping using a high-temperature carbonization with dicyandiamide (DCDA) and during the purification process using a mixture of H₂SO₄ and HNO₃. The consequences of these aftertreatments towards the ORR and HER electrocatalytic activity are also presented.

Experimental

Synthesis of carbon materials from CO₂

The carbon material was synthesized in an alumina crucible contained in a cylindrical stainless-steel reactor. The eutectic mixture of Li₂CO₃ and K₂CO₃, into which 10 wt.% of NiO was added, was poured into an Al₂O₃ crucible. The mix was heated to 540 °C to create a

molten electrolyte, and the cathode and anode were inserted into the salt. A coiled steel wire was used as the cathode and a graphite rod as the anode. CO₂ (99.995%, Elme Messer) was flown through the electrolyte during the synthesis at a flow rate of 20 SCCM to regenerate the carbonate salt. A potential of 4 V was applied to the electrodes for the electrolysis of CO₂ into solid carbon and oxygen gas. After 1 h of electrolysis, the electrodes were removed from the electrolyte and cooled to room temperature in air. After that, the cathode was inserted into a beaker, which was then filled with 5 M HCl (p.a., Fluka) to remove the remaining electrolyte from the material and from the surface of the electrode to allow for the material to be detached. The suspension of the carbon material in HCl was then vacuum filtered, washed with Milli-Q water to a neutral pH and then dried. The resulting carbon material is noted as CO₂-Ni in the manuscript. For examining the effect of nitrogen doping of the CO₂-Ni material towards its electrocatalytic activity, it was mixed with 20 times its weight of DCDA (Sigma-Aldrich) and polyvinylpyrrolidone (Sigma-Aldrich) in a beaker containing ethanol for 2 h. After this the mixture was dried and pyrolyzed in a tube furnace at 800 °C for 1 hour in Ar (5.0, Elme Messer) flow. The material was then removed and weighed. This material is noted as CO₂-NiN in the manuscript. For removing “bare” nickel oxide particles not covered with graphitic carbon layers, the catalyst was then treated for 8 h with a mixture of 0.5 M HNO₃ (Sigma-Aldrich) and 0.5 M H₂SO₄ (Sigma-Aldrich) at 50 °C. Then the catalyst was pyrolyzed for 1 h at 800 °C again to remove the adsorbed species from the nitrogen doped carbon and the final material is noted as CO₂-NiNO_x in the following text.

Physical characterisation of the CO₂-derived catalysts

Characterization of the surface morphology of the catalyst materials was done with ZEISS FE-SEM Ultra 55 and ZEISS Crossbeam 540 scanning electron microscopes (SEMs). The

acceleration voltage of SEM measurements for high resolution imaging was 4.0 kV (In-lens SE detection), low magnification images were acquired at 5.0 kV.

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) microphotos were taken using a FEI Tecnai F20 TEM operating at 80 kV. Bright field TEM images were captured with a Gatan OneView camera. Scanning TEM (STEM) Energy-Dispersive X-ray (EDX) and Electron Energy-Loss Spectroscopy (EELS) were performed in a FEI Tecnai Osiris S/TEM at 80 kV acceleration voltage. The EDX signal was collected using a Super-X detector and the EELS signal with a Gatan Enfium spectrometer.

The adsorption and desorption isotherms were measured using N₂ sorption analysis (KELVIN 1042 Sorptometer, Costech Microanalytical SC). The samples were outgassed at 200 °C for 1 h before adsorption measurements to remove guest species from the surface. The carrier gas was helium, and N₂ (purity 99.999%) was used as an adsorptive gas. Nitrogen adsorption points were collected at relative pressures (p/p_0) from 0.025 to 0.93 at the liquid N₂ temperature of -196.15 °C. The specific surface area was derived from the Brunauer-Emmet-Teller (BET) theory and the two-dimensional non-local density functional theory model for carbons with heterogeneous surfaces (2D-NLDFT) using the SAIEUS software. DFT surface area and pore volumes were also determined using the 2D-NLDFT model.

Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were collected on Malvern PANalytical Xpert³ with 45 kV beam voltage and 40 mA beam current using Cu K α radiation ($\lambda=0.154$ nm).

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was used to determine the elemental composition of the surface, using an AXIS ULTRA DLD spectrometer. The monochromatic Al K α anode X-ray source (1486.6 eV) was operated at 150 W and 15 kV. A hemispherical energy analyser at hybrid lens mode was operated at a pass energy of 160 eV for survey spectra and 20 eV for core-level spectra. Aperture was set to field of view Slot mode (300 x 700 μm^2). The relative surface contents of elements were calculated using peak integration and the sensitivity factors

provided by the original analysis Kratos Vision 2.2.10 software with Shirley background correction. The bulk elemental composition was determined by total X-ray fluorescence (TXRF) spectrometry using a Bruker S2 Picofox TXRF spectrometer.

Electrode preparation and electrochemical characterization

The electrochemical measurements of the CO₂-derived catalysts' activity towards the ORR and HER were undertaken using the RDE method. Typically, 2 mg of the catalyst was first suspended in ethanol containing 3 μ l of the 2 wt.% aQAPS-S₁₄ ionomer solution from Hephass Energy. The suspension was sonicated for 30 s using a sonication probe and for at least 30 minutes in a sonication bath. The suspension of the catalyst material was then pipetted in 4 μ l aliquots onto a clean glassy carbon (GC, Goodfellow Cambridge Ltd., UK) disks to reach a loading of 0.2 mg cm⁻². The GC disks were cleaned prior to this by polishing with 1 μ m and 0.3 μ m particle size alumina slurries and then sonicated first ethanol and then in Milli-Q water for residue removal. The electrocatalytic activity of the coated electrodes was studied in O₂-saturated (99.999%, Elme Messer AS, Estonia) 0.1 M KOH (VWR) in a five-neck glass electrochemical cell. A platinum wire in a glass frit served as the counter electrode and a saturated calomel electrode (SCE, SI Analytics) separated from the cell by a Luggin capillary was used as the reference electrode. For measuring ORR activity, polarisation curves were recorded from 0 to -1.2 V vs the SCE using the Gamry potentiostat 1010E (Gamry Instruments, USA) with a sweep rate of 1.67 mV s⁻¹ and a step of 25 mV, giving a dwell time of 15 s. An OrigaTrod controller was used to control the rotating electrode (OrigaLys ElectroChem SAS, France). The electrode rotation speeds were: (1) 400, (2) 800, (3) 1200, (4) 1600, (5) 1900, (6) 2400 and (7) 3600 rpm. For comparison, ORR polarization curves were also recorded on GC electrodes modified with 0.1 mg cm⁻² of the 47.0 wt.% Pt/C catalyst from Tanaka.

Results and discussion

Physical characterization of the CO₂-derived catalysts

Morphology and textural properties of the CO₂-derived catalysts

The morphology of the carbon materials synthesized from CO₂ is depicted in Figure 1. Fig1a shows a large area overview of the undoped material, with etched shell-like features on display. Some lighter spots depicting Ni particles are also seen. Fig1c shows a TEM image of the surface of the carbon material, with a mixture of graphitic carbon layers and amorphous regions visible. After nitrogen doping, the surface characteristics of the carbon material change significantly: a more strongly etched morphology is seen on Fig1b (which can be ascribed to the partial etching of the surface of the carbon material by products of DCDA decomposition, such as NH₃ and carbon nitride gases^{50,51}). DCDA is a well-known nitrogen precursor, which is cheap, has a large relative content of nitrogen atoms, and can also produce CNTs during thermal annealing, which can further enhance the activity of the catalyst. Nitrogen doped CNTs appear in the SEM images here as well, as nickel nanoparticles are known to catalyze the formation of N-doped CNTs from DCDA in addition to forming CNTs during the synthesis of carbon from the carbonate melt.⁵² These nanotubes have a bamboo-shaped morphology and are capped off with the nickel oxide particles (Fig1e), which in turn are covered in graphitic N-doped carbon.

Figure 1. SEM and TEM micrographs of the CO₂-Ni (a,c) and CO₂-NiN materials (b,d,e).

Figure 2 shows an overview of the deposited nickel oxide particles on the carbon material. As seen from Fig2a, undoped carbon is deposited from a Li₂CO₃-K₂CO₃ melt and presents nickel oxide particles on the surface, aggregating in clusters. Fig2d shows a close-up of one of these clusters, with nickel oxide nanoparticles sized around 50-100 nm visible. After nitrogen doping (Fig 2b), further clustering of the Ni/NiO can be seen as the high temperature treatment induces the smaller particles to agglomerate into larger ones and clusters (Fig 2e). However, a closer look at the surface of the carbon shows that even in regions with no clusters of Ni/NiO, a homogeneous coverage of Ni/NiO nanoparticles is present. As carbon nanomaterials can contain significant amount of secondary phases after synthesis (as shown here), such as residual metal catalyst impurities uncovered by carbon layers which can dissolve during ORR or HER operation or otherwise decrease the final activity by giving the catalyst dead mass, it's essential to remove them to increase their activity. Acid treatment

with H₂SO₄, HNO₃ or HCl has been shown to be the most effective towards removing such impurities.⁵³ After the acid leaching process (Fig 2c), most of the Ni/NiO agglomerates are removed, as these are exposed Ni/NiO particles that are easily removed by the acid treatment, leaving behind only Ni species covered with graphitic carbon layers (Fig 2f). To more accurately determine the content of nickel in the catalyst materials, TXRF analysis was undertaken. The bulk Ni content of the CO₂-Ni catalyst was 14.3 wt.%, 10.6 wt.% for the CO₂-NiN catalyst and 2.2 wt.% for the CO₂-NiNO_x catalyst as-determined by TXRF, which supports the conclusions made by using the SEM-EDX analysis. The gradual loss in nickel content, in combination with the positive effects seen in the electrocatalytic activity is further proof of the necessity of the acid treatment.

Figure 2. SEM micrographs of (a,d) CO₂-Ni, (b,e) CO₂-NiN and (c,f) CO₂-NiNO_x.

Table 1. Elemental composition of the CO₂-derived materials as determined by SEM-EDX.

Catalyst	C at.%	O at.%	Ni at.%	K at.%
CO ₂ -Ni	64.5	25.9	7.9	1.3
CO ₂ -NiN	66.3	29.5	3.2	-

CO2-NiNOx	89.3	8.8	0.9	-
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Table 1 shows the elemental composition of the catalyst materials. Owing to a high content of NiO, the oxygen content in CO2-Ni and CO2-NiN is quite high, with the nickel content dropping with every synthesis step as the nickel particles not attached to the carbon or covered in carbon are gradually removed. Sub-at.% contents of Cl, Fe, Si and S were also detected.

Analytical STEM-EDX was carried out to understand the properties of the catalyst and the interplay between Ni, N and C at the nanoscale (Figure 3). The carbon, as observed in SEM, appears in either hollow shell-like structures or denser, but still highly porous, aggregates. Chemical analysis indicates that the material is mostly pure, with limited contamination that can be ascribed to the steel cathode (Fe, Cr). CO2-Ni and CO2-NiN show diffuse presence of Ni particles up to about 100 nm in size. A STEM-EELS spectrum from a representative thin area of CO2-NiN indicates the presence of graphitic carbon; nitrogen and oxygen are also detectable.

Figure 3. (Top) STEM-EDX maps showing the chemical distribution of C, O and Ni in samples CO₂, CO₂-Ni and CO₂-NiN. The scale bars represent 500 nm. (Bottom) EEL spectrum of a representative thin area of sample CO₂-NiN. The visible edges are related to carbon (284 eV), nitrogen (401 eV) and oxygen (532 eV).

Figure 4. XPS survey spectra (a,c,e) and N1s core-level spectra (b,d,f) for CO₂-Ni, CO₂-NiN and CO₂-NiNO_x samples, respectively.

To compare the relative contents of elements on the surface and bulk of the material, XPS was utilized to determine the surface elemental content in the CO₂-derived catalyst materials.

Figure 4a shows the XPS survey spectra of the undoped CO₂-Ni material, with prominent

C1s and O1s peaks visible, as well as a minor Ni2p peak. There was no nitrogen present on the surface of the material as visible from Figure 4b. The carbon content was somewhat higher than in the bulk of the material (Table 2), with carbon making up 80.9 at.% of the surface content compared to 64.5 at.% in the bulk (Table 1). The oxygen content and nickel contents, however, are more telling, as the surface nickel content is nearly 8 times lower than in the bulk, showing that most of the nickel is located deeper inside the carbon material. After the doping (Figure 4c), the surface nickel content drops to 0.2 at.%, as more nickel/NiO particles are covered in carbon layers (when used as catalytic particles for CNT growth from DCDA). The overall nitrogen content determined on the surface of the CO₂-NiN material was 3.7 at.% (Figure 4d), with the relative contents of different N species also given in Table 2. Acid leaching and secondary pyrolysis of the catalyst material (Figure 4e) removes most of the surface oxygen content as 1) the „bare“ nickel/nickel oxide particles are removed and 2) the surface is reduced due to the secondary pyrolysis in Ar. The nitrogen content also drops from 3.7 to 1.8 at.% as doped carbon can also be susceptible to oxidation by acid, however, it is important to note that most of the lost surface nitrogen comes from pyrrolic N (Figure 4f), which is known to have a lower activity towards the ORR than pyridinic and graphitic N species.

Table 2. Surface elemental compositions and nitrogen speciation of the CO₂-derived catalyst materials as determined by XPS.

Catalyst	C at.%	N at.%	O at.%	Ni at.%	Pyridinic N at.%	Graphitic N at.%	Pyrrolic N at.%	N-O at.%
CO₂-Ni	80.9	-	13.3	1.0	-	-	-	-
CO₂- NiN	64.3	3.7	20.2	0.2	1.4	0.7	1.4	0.2

CO2-	94.6	1.8	2.8	0.2	0.9	0.4	0.4	0.1
NiNO_x								

Next to its elemental composition, the porosity and surface area of a catalyst material are the most important properties to maximize its electrocatalytic abilities. The textural properties of the CO₂-Ni, CO₂-NiN and CO₂-NiNO_x catalysts derived from N₂ physisorption measurements are given in Table 3 and the pore size distributions shown in Figure 5a. The surface area of the materials was similar to other common carbon supports, with somewhat more microporosity (the SSA of Vulcan XC-72 is around 250 m² g⁻¹), however, none of these materials are produced from sustainable carbon sources and instead put more pressure on the environment as they are mostly produced from soot and other fossil fuel products. The CO₂-Ni and CO₂-NiN materials had rather similar SSA's and PSD's (with the CO₂-NiN exhibiting a larger surface area due to the etching of carbon visible from SEM, which formed more porosity), however, for the CO₂-NiNO_x material, the surface area was decreased by nearly half. This is a product of the graphitization of microporous carbon due to the presence of NiO during the high-temperature treatment and the prior oxidation, which preferentially removes high-surface area amorphous, rather than graphitic, carbon.⁵⁴ A decrease in surface area commonly reduces the activity of electrocatalysts since it also decreases the accessibility of active sites. Here, however, since there are other, more impactful processes taking place during the pyrolysis (the formation of new active sites that are more accessible), the effect is negligible.

Figure 5. (a) Pore size distributions for the CO_2 -derived catalyst materials and powder X-ray diffraction patterns for the (b) CO_2 -Ni, (c) CO_2 -NiN and (d) CO_2 -NiNOx materials.

Table 3. Textural properties of the CO_2 -derived catalyst materials.

Catalyst	$S_{\text{BET}}, \text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$	$S_{\text{DFT}}, \text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$	$V_{\text{tot(DFT)}}, \text{cm}^3 \text{g}^{-1}$	$V_{\mu(\text{DFT})}, \text{cm}^3 \text{g}^{-1}$
CO2-Ni	187.1	186.4	0.184	0.064
CO2-NiN	202.3	185.2	0.181	0.069
CO2-NiNOx	107.4	104.2	0.086	0.037

The powder X-ray diffraction patterns of the three catalyst materials are shown in Figure 5b-d. In the CO_2 -Ni material, the crystalline Ni is present mostly as NiO, as can be expected from using NiO as the catalyst for carbon deposition. When the material is doped with DCDA, the exposed NiO becomes Ni as the reducing agents from the decomposition of DCDA also reduce the nickel present. After acid leaching, the only Ni left is the small

amount of Ni which is covered in graphitic carbon and therefore protected from both reducing agents and acids. Another prominent feature is the graphitic peak of carbon at $26.8^{\circ}2\theta$, which becomes relatively more intense as the Ni content is reduced and the carbon becomes more graphitic with subsequent heat treatments.

3.2. Electrocatalytic activity of the CO₂-derived catalysts towards the ORR and HER

The ORR activity of the CO₂-NiN and CO₂-NiNO_x materials on glassy carbon electrodes was tested in a 0.1 M KOH solution saturated with O₂. CO₂-Ni was omitted from ORR testing since undoped carbon is known to have negligible activity towards the ORR. DCDA is a cheap and environmentally benign compound commonly used as a fertilizer, which has been long known to be a very effective doping agent for carbon materials. By pyrolyzing the CO₂-derived material in the presence of DCDA, the material is doped with nitrogen as shown from the XPS results, creating active sites for the ORR and HER. Figure 6a shows ORR polarization curves recorded with CO₂-NiN catalyst material. The first reduction wave begins at -186 mV vs SCE and a second reduction wave can be seen at -0.7 V vs SCE, which is commonly related to quinone-type groups on the surface of the electrode.⁵⁵

Figure 6b shows the Koutecky-Levich (K-L) plots derived from ORR polarization data with the inset demonstrating the number of electrons transferred per O₂ molecule (n). The n value was calculated from the K-L equation:⁵⁶

$$\frac{1}{j} = \frac{1}{j_k} + \frac{1}{j_d} = -\frac{1}{nFkc_{O_2}^b} - \frac{1}{0.62nFD_{O_2}^{2/3}\nu^{-1/6}\omega^{1/2}c_{O_2}^b}, \quad (1),$$

where ω is the rotation rate (rad s^{-1}), F is the Faraday constant (96485 C mol^{-1}), C_{O_2} is the concentration of oxygen in the bulk ($1.2 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol cm}^{-3}$),⁵⁷ j_k and j_d are the kinetic and diffusion-limited current densities, D_{O_2} is the diffusion coefficient of oxygen ($1.9 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$),⁵⁷ k is the rate constant for O₂ reduction, and ν is the kinematic viscosity of the solution ($0.01 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$).⁵⁸

The n value for the CO₂-NiN catalyst is even somewhat below 2 at positive potential values (likely due to poor oxygen transport inside the catalyst layer, which can skew the K-L analysis results towards lower n values⁵⁹), but increases to over 2 at more negative potentials, with the K-L plots also giving significant intercept values when extrapolated. This means that the main product of ORR on the CO₂-NiN catalyst is OH₂⁻ in alkaline media and there is a significant kinetic limitation to the ORR on this catalyst. The CO₂-NiN material would thus likely be more suitable for hydrogen peroxide production rather than a fuel cell electrode. Nevertheless, this result shows that a cheap catalyst can be synthesized by the CO₂ electrolysis method in a sustainable way by capturing CO₂ from the environment instead of producing it.

Figure 6. ORR linear sweep polarisation curves from GC electrodes modified with the (a) CO₂-NiN and (c) CO₂-NiNO_x material recorded in O₂-saturated 0.1 M KOH and Koutecky-Levich plots (b,d) calculated from the ORR data with the number of electrons transferred per O₂ molecule (n) in the inset. $v = 1.67 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$, $\omega =$ (1) 400, (2) 800, (3) 1200, (4) 1600, (5) 1900, (6) 2400 and (7) 3600 rpm. ORR polarization (e) and HER (f) linear sweep polarization

curves for the CO₂-Ni, CO₂-NiN and CO₂-NiNO_x materials recorded in O₂- and N₂-saturated 0.1 M KOH, respectively.

Figure 7c shows the oxygen reduction polarization curves for CO₂-NiNO_x, with the corresponding K-L plots given in Figure 7d. The onset potential of ORR for this electrocatalyst was at -163 mV vs SCE, somewhat more positive than the CO₂-NiN material, with the *n* value also 2 at more positive potentials and reaching 3 at -0.9 V vs SCE. The second reduction wave at -0.7 V was also present for this material. This means that at more positive potentials a lot of hydrogen peroxide is produced, but at more negative potentials the oxygen species on the surface of the catalyst also take part in the reduction process and in the end, all of the oxygen is reduced to water, giving an overall *n* of three.

Figure 6e shows a comparison of the ORR activities of the two CO₂-derived catalyst materials. For better comparison with values from the literature, the potential values were converted to RHE by calibrating the SCE used for the experiments. Clearly, the CO₂-NiNO_x material was more active towards the ORR. The likely reason for this is a better speciation of nitrogen (this material had less pyrrolic N, which is known to catalyze the two-electron ORR).⁶⁰ Pyridinic N is commonly known to donate a *p*-electron into the aromatic π -system of the carbon plane, destabilizing the carbon atoms next to it and enhancing oxygen adsorption as well as providing local charge.^{61,62} Graphitic nitrogen is also known to contribute to the four-electron pathway due to its higher electronegativity when compared to carbon, but no certain determinations have been made as to the most active moieties towards two- and four-electron ORR due to the difficulty synthesizing selectively doped materials.^{62,63} The nickel oxide nanoparticles encapsulated by the N-doped carbon also contribute to the ORR activity by further modifying the electronic properties of the carbon on top of it and changing the adsorption energies of ORR intermediates (in this case, enhancing the adsorption of OH₂⁻ so

that it does not desorb prior to further reduction to OH^-).^{27,64,65} Recent studies have shown that the situation in alkaline media is further complicated by adsorbed OH^- species, which can further complicate the situation by facilitating a 2-electron transfer mechanism in the outer Helmholtz plane due to the difficulty of reaching the doped carbon surface in such conditions.^{25,66} The commercial 47.0 wt.% Pt/C catalyst from Tanaka had an ORR onset potential of -48 mV vs SCE, which is much more positive than the onset potential of both $\text{CO}_2\text{-NiN}$ and $\text{CO}_2\text{-NiNO}_x$ materials, showing that there is room for yet more optimizations to achieve the level of commercial catalysts for the CO_2 -derived materials. Compared to state-of-the-art catalysts such as Pt/C but also some NPMCs, the activity might be somewhat lower for the materials presented here, especially for the ORR. However, the idea behind this manuscript is not to present a perfectly optimized material, but rather a novel synthesis pathway. Compared to other synthesis methods, the one presented here captures CO_2 instead of producing it and directly turns it into a useful catalyst material. It is clear that the ORR activity of the CO_2 -derived nitrogen and nickel-doped catalysts is not sufficient for fuel cell use, as is. However, it does present a fascinating new pathway towards new and improved doped carbon materials, and most importantly, a pathway with significant CO_2 captured during the synthesis of the material.

The HER LSV polarization curves for the $\text{CO}_2\text{-Ni}$, $\text{CO}_2\text{-NiN}$ and $\text{CO}_2\text{-NiNO}_x$ materials are given in Fig 6f. Without nitrogen doping, the HER activity of the catalyst is rather low, with the current not reaching 10 mA cm^{-2} in the studied potential range. $\text{CO}_2\text{-NiN}$ and $\text{CO}_2\text{-NiNO}_x$, materials, on the other hand, show excellent HER activity with $E_{@10 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}}$ values of -337 mV and -446 mV vs RHE, respectively. The reasons for the HER activity of these materials are much the same as for the ORR activity, however, in this case, the material not leached in acid was somewhat more active, likely due to the overall higher surface area and higher nickel oxide content. The $E_{@10 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}}$ values reached are very competitive values in

comparison with other catalysts in the literature based on carbon-encapsulated metal nanoparticles, which are commonly derived from expensive and CO₂-intensive precursors such as MOFs or CNTs made by CVD (further discussed below).^{27,67,76–85,68–75} In this sense, the CO₂-derived materials shown here do not even have a direct competitor as all other catalysts presented before have always had a large positive CO₂ footprint, which is in some cases reduced by using precursors such as biomass or waste, but never before has any HER or ORR catalyst captured CO₂ simply by its synthesis.

Table S1 shows a comparison of the catalysts presented here with some of the best NPMCs from the literature. Compared to these examples, the HER activity of the CO₂-NiNO_x material is quite competitive, with some of the best catalyst materials presented having a somewhat more positive potential at 10 mA cm⁻². However, it is important to note that many of these have quite expensive and unsustainable precursors, such as MOFs or other polymer networks,^{72,75,77,81,83,84} ion-exchange resins,⁷³ carbon nanofibers,⁷⁴ 1,10-phenanthroline and MgO templates,⁷⁶ nickel foam,^{79,85} or carbon nanotubes.⁸² Even in works where the precursors are cheap and abundant, the methods used are often tedious and difficult to scale up, such as long hydrothermal or plasma treatments,^{68,78} which increase the overall environmental impact of the product as well. Compared to every single one of these competitors, the CO₂-NiNO_x material has the advantage of using a precursor which, if removed from the environment, as this synthesis process does, has a positive impact on the environment and can be sustainable. By using CO₂ as the starting material for catalysts that can in turn also affect the environment positively, we can ultimately alleviate the effects of climate change faster than by using non-sustainable precursors.

Conclusions

In conclusion, we demonstrate a novel type of sustainable catalyst materials that were derived from CO₂ by electrolysis of a Li₂CO₃-K₂CO₃ melt using steel cathode and graphite anode at

540 °C. An addition of 10 wt.% NiO was used to increase the degree of graphitization of the carbon material and induce the growth of CNTs both during the electrolysis and nitrogen doping, which was done using DCDA at 800 °C for 1 h in Ar flow. The ORR onset potential of the CO₂-NiN material, which catalyzed mostly the two-electron reduction of oxygen, was -186 mV vs SCE, while its $E_{@10\text{ mA cm}^{-2}}$ value for HER was -337 mV, the latter being very competitive with some of the best catalysts based on nitrogen and metal doped carbon. We further demonstrate that leaching the catalyst in a mixture of 0.5 M H₂SO₄ and HNO₃ increased the ORR activity, while decreasing the HER activity, leading to a conclusion that the catalytic active sites for these reactions are fundamentally different in this type of materials. Overall, this method shows promise for synthesizing ORR and HER catalysts with no CO₂ footprint for a clean transition from a carbon-based economy to a hydrogen-based one.

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Supporting information

Table containing comparison of HER activity of the CO₂-NiN and CO₂-NiNO_x materials with

other NPMCs from the literature.

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Synopsis: Bifunctional catalyst materials for the oxygen reduction and hydrogen evolution reactions are synthesized by capturing CO₂.